

Building Open Source Opportunities for Students in Tech (BOOST): A Follow-Up Study with BOOST Graduates

How Mentorship and Open Source Projects as Innovative Work-Based Learning Opportunities Impacted Computer Science Graduates in the Workplace

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Executive Summary

Building Open Source Opportunities for Students in Tech (BOOST) is a new and innovative capstone project at Green River College (GRC) that was designed in response to pandemic-era challenges and inequities in computer science internships. Developed in partnership with Mentors in Tech (MinT) and CodeDay, BOOST pairs students with industry mentors to complete open source software projects within a capstone course sequence. Students work 10–15 hours weekly, both in class and with mentors, gaining technical training, professional guidance, and a paid, flexible experience — experience that is critical for adult learners, low-income students, and others who face barriers to traditional internships.

BOOST now has graduates who have been in the workforce for one to three years, presenting an opportunity for greater insight into the ways in which participating in BOOST as an undergraduate can influence their performance and experience in the workforce. As such, this study follows up on our prior BOOST evaluation, seeking to **understand in what ways, if at all, the BOOST model impacted the workforce experience of its graduates**, including (a) applying for, interviewing for, and/or landing jobs, including in their field of study; b) providing work-based experience that was representative of the work they encountered in their jobs; (c) creating the conditions for graduates to experience promotions within their workplace; and (d) other impacts identified by graduates.

Graduates interviewed for this study consistently described BOOST as one of the most workplace-relevant elements of their degree. They reported that the open source projects mirrored the complexity of industry work, requiring them to collaborate, manage tasks, and adopt professional problem-solving approaches. Many highlighted that the capstone was the closest academic experience to “real-world” employment, giving them confidence to contribute quickly in their first jobs. Several noted the value of showcasing their open source projects on resumes and in interviews, with some securing jobs or promotions directly because of the skills and experiences gained.

Importantly, graduates credited BOOST with both technical proficiency and soft skills, such as communication, teamwork, and project management, that set them apart from peers. Many felt the experience accelerated their career trajectory, with some reporting faster promotion rates than colleagues who lacked comparable real-world preparation.

Overall, findings suggest BOOST effectively bridges the gap between classroom learning and professional practice, offering an equitable alternative to traditional internships that positions GRC graduates for long-term career success.

Background & Methods

Background on BOOST¹

Internships during computer science (CS) programs are vital in helping college students secure high-paying jobs in the tech industry upon graduation (Strada, 2024). However, COVID-19 left graduating students a suboptimal job market. Opportunities for internships were down by nearly 50 percent (Stansell, 2020a), and job openings for pandemic graduates were down over 60 percent from pre-pandemic rates (Stansell, 2020b). Further, internships that are available are often rife with inequity, making it difficult for adult learners, lower income students, and other minoritized populations to access these coveted roles (Francisco, 2020; Singer, 2023; Strada, 2023). In addition, students at smaller and less well-known institutions have a particularly difficult time accessing work-based learning opportunities for a variety of reasons, though they are the population that might benefit most (Hang et al., 2023). Such trends were particularly alarming at Green River College (GRC) in Puget Sound, a geographic region of Washington state where well-paying tech jobs anchor the economy.

In response to these realities, and in an effort to best prepare CS students for a competitive tech industry workforce upon graduation, GRC, Mentors in Tech (MinT), and CodeDay collaborated to develop a new and innovative work-based learning model, Building Open Source Opportunities for Students in Tech (BOOST). Through BOOST, the collaborators hoped to “increase the number of students who participate in internships as well as provide students with access to experiential learning opportunities that provide similar value to students as a traditional industry internship” (Hang et al., 2023).

With BOOST’s distinct approach, CS students work in teams on an open source software project and are paired with mentors, who are currently professionals in tech fields. Mentors guide students as they work through their open source projects, helping students solve problems, adopt workplace-appropriate solutions and approaches to problems, and keep pace in their work progress. Students spend six hours weekly on projects in class with faculty and at least four hours weekly collaborating with teammates and meeting with their mentors. Students are paid stipends for out-of-class work at no less than the state’s minimum wage (~\$15/hour), ensuring low-income, working students can participate (Menezes et al., 2022).

About the organizations

Green River College (GRC) is a public community college in Puget Sound, Washington and federally recognized as a minority-serving institution (MUREP, 2023). Its Information Technology department offers two- and four-year tech degrees and received the Aspen Institute’s 2020 Excellence and Equity in Community College STEM award (LeRoi-Schmidt, 2022). Green River is one of 187 community colleges in the country to offer bachelor’s degrees (CCBA & Bragg, 2024).

CodeDay is a non-profit organization that provides opportunities in STEM for high school and college students. It is the creator of CodeDay Labs, an open source internship program that pairs students with industry professionals as project mentors as students work on an open source software project (Hang et al., 2023).

Mentors in Tech (MinT) is a social impact organization that helps tech students at smaller, less well-known, accessible, and affordable colleges navigate and launch their careers through structured mentoring programs (Mentors in Tech, n.d.).

¹The BOOST initiative was formerly referred to and written about as the TechConnect Capstone (TCC). TCC and BOOST represent the same work but under different names.

About Open Source Projects and the BOOST Collaboration

For BOOST, MinT and CodeDay recruit and train industry mentors and work with faculty to identify appropriate open source projects for students. Open source projects are defined as “an industry engagement experience in which students work on a new or existing software project, licensed under an open source license” (Menezes et al., 2022). Such projects “allow for students to make open source contributions and project experience to be visible and shareable on their resumes, in interviews, and their portfolios/public profiles (e.g. GitHub, LinkedIn)” (Hang et al., 2023). Examples of open source projects that BOOST students have completed include an F-Prime project, for which NASA is a contributor and sponsor, and the Flutter project, for which Google is a contributor and sponsor — both of which reach thousands to millions of users.

The BOOST model has three components of a comprehensive work-based learning program: (1) aligned classroom and workplace learning; (2) application of academic, technical, and employability skills in a work setting; and, (3) support from classroom or workplace mentors. BOOST embeds “capstone” projects within an upper-division, two-course, 10 credit hour sequence in GRC’s Bachelor of Applied Science in Software Development degree program.

To find mentors, MinT and CodeDay rely on their extensive network and call out to industry partners and professionals to find those who might be interested in serving as mentors. Mentors typically have 15 or more years of experience and often manage teams in their work roles. They’re often working at companies like Apple, Amazon, Microsoft, or other large tech companies or have experience in tech at Fortune 500 companies

in other verticals (e.g., software engineer at a Visa or airlines). MinT shares the scope of their involvement as mentors, including hours and workload. Once industry professionals self-select to serve as mentors, they partake in an onboarding session and trainings, which includes setting expectations for their commitment and training around how to best support students.

MinT and CodeDay then identify open source projects that are interesting, meaningful, and achievable when considering the students’ skill level. Projects often include smaller bugs or features found within an extensive codebase, requiring students to understand the context of a much larger system in order to complete their work correctly. The intent of the open source projects is to engage students in an end-to-end software development process that is not seen or experienced in the classroom, giving them firsthand experience in how such work is done. MinT brings these projects to instructors, who also assess the projects for suitability and alignment with student skills and time commitment and who present the project options to students. Students ultimately get to select their open source project.

Students assemble in groups of 3–5 and typically work with three mentors. The mentors often have a direct connection with the open source community, which helps them guide students through the work.

Student groups meet with their mentors 1–3 times a week, with most groups meeting formally twice a week and informally more often through communications channels for questions and troubleshooting. Additionally, students meet in class with instructors twice a week. Overall, students are expected to spend four hours in class and around 10 hours outside of class on the BOOST model each week.

Insights on BOOST During the Undergraduate Experience

An earlier developmental evaluation of the capstone (Meza & Pawlicki, 2024) provided insights into GRC students' experiences with BOOST. Findings included:

- Students found the BOOST projects relevant, particularly in terms of communication, teamwork, project management, and developing computer language proficiency.
- All students shared that they felt better prepared for a job having participated in the BOOST model and more prepared to tackle the job market after the capstone project course.
- This mode of internship was also helpful to adult students and those who may not have otherwise been able to complete traditional internships.
- Faculty and staff found using open source projects over traditional employer internships was a key for the BOOST model's success, particularly because of the way the open source projects simulate a workplace experience.
- Staff also stressed the importance of mentors in the BOOST model because of the structure and feedback they provide. Instructors also saw growth in students, including students' confidence and engagement in the project. (Meza & Pawlicki, 2024, p. 4)

While some challenges emerged in the study, such as some students' difficulty in dedicating the appropriate time to the project and challenges related to assessment, scale, and sustainability, findings point to the program's success. Overall, our prior study found that BOOST gives students real-world experience in new software, in working with a collaborative, professional team, and in learning methods that are of a workplace caliber. This mentored, open source project

model might overcome some of the challenges associated with traditional internships while still providing valuable experience and contacts, especially for underserved students and adult learners (Meza & Pawlicki, 2024, p. 4).

Following Up: Impacts of BOOST After Graduation

Now in its fourth year of operation at GRC, BOOST has a rich assembly of graduates who have entered the workforce, providing us an opportunity to better understand the effectiveness and longer-term impacts of the BOOST model on graduates' careers. As such, **our team sought to follow up with graduates to learn more about their experience in the workforce and how BOOST may or may not have impacted it.** Built on the hypothesis that the BOOST model would (1) better prepare graduates for the workforce, (2) provide them experience through the open source project that is more representative of the work they would encounter in the tech industry, and (3) help them as they navigated applying to and landing jobs, our interviews with graduates allowed us to explore to what extent these hypotheses were actualized in practice.

About the Study

Developed in collaboration with GRC, MinT, and CodeDay, and following up on our prior developmental evaluation, this follow-up study sought to **understand in what ways, if at all, the BOOST model impacted the workforce experience of its graduates**, including (a) applying for, interviewing for, and/or landing jobs, including in their field of study; b) providing work-based experience that was representative of the work they encountered in their jobs; (c) creating the conditions for graduates to experience promotions within their workplace; and (d) other impacts identified by graduates.

Data Sources

The data corpus for this study included: (a) qualitative interviews with graduates who had participated in the BOOST capstone experience; (b) a short survey completed by interviewees, which collected demographic information, work status, and information related to technology experience; and (c) artifacts, including program descriptions and other written material related to the BOOST model.

Nine graduates were interviewed for this study. All nine completed a capstone project during their tenure as students at Green River College. Of the nine graduates, two identified as female and seven as male. Respondents ranged in age, from 22–56 years old.

For all interviews, a semi-structured interview protocol was used. Interviews were recorded and transcribed using Zoom’s built-in transcription process. Using an open-coding structure, the interviews were coded and analyzed using a computer assisted qualitative data analysis software, MAXQDA. From these codes, we began sorting and aggregating codes into major themes, presented in the findings section. We engaged in an iterative process while remaining close to the data. Overall, we followed Robert Yin’s (2016) approach for disassembling data (i.e., creating open codes), reassembling data (i.e., categorical coding and looking for intersections of open codes), and interpreting data (i.e., drawing out themes from the coded data).

Findings

Through qualitative interviews, graduates of the BOOST program shared an overall positive perspective of the capstone experience. They felt like the open source project mirrored an internship experience but was more flexible for their schedule and pushed them past their comfort zone. They felt that the experience was a valuable addition to their resume, playing a vital role in helping them demonstrate their skillsets and ultimately land jobs in their field. After entering the workforce, most graduates felt that the BOOST experience had replicated their workplace environment and responsibilities, leaving them prepared for their jobs and, in some cases, better prepared than their peers. Some reported that they felt the experience had led to more — and more frequent — promotions. More details of the graduates' insights follow.

Graduate Profiles

We spoke with nine graduates of the GRC Software Development BAS program, all having graduated between 2021 and 2024. **All graduates earned an associate degree in the Washington Community and Technical College system prior to completing their BAS**, including many who did so at GRC or through Washington's Running Start (dual enrollment) initiative. Some graduates have continued on to additional learning, including a graduate who is now pursuing an additional bachelor's degree in cyber security and another who is in a master's degree program in the tech field. Most graduates are native to Washington and described that attending GRC allowed them to stay close to home. While one graduate is not currently employed, the others reported a range of careers in the tech industry, including software engineers at major corporations like **Boeing, Costco, and Microsoft**, an individual software developer working for an array of companies, and one in a software-style job in aerospace. Importantly,

the graduate who reported that they were not presently employed is currently a student pursuing an additional degree.

Overall Perspective

The nine graduates interviewed largely had a very positive perception of their BOOST capstone experience. One graduate felt that participating in the experience was a "no brainer" because of the practical work-based experience it provided; he felt it was "hands down" a vital experience for students who wanted to be a professional software developer. More specifically, graduates mentioned that the capstone was important because it gave them experience that was different from their other coursework. One graduate described that BOOST was "a little more difficult and pushed students out of the same things that we had been doing over and over again in the group projects we had done in previous years." This graduate shared that the experience gave students the opportunity to try different skills and tasks that they otherwise wouldn't be exposed to in a traditional, client-based project experience. They shared:

"Personally, I think that everybody should have to do an open source contribution during their bachelor's degree, because I feel like it was the most closely resembling real-world work. And it's something that you can easily put on your resume and it made an impact."

Overall, graduates shared that the experience gave them technical skillsets in technologies new to them while also giving them experience collaborating closely with other people. Of the skills learned, one graduate shared:

“For the [BOOST] projects themselves, the most valuable pieces that I got from that was working directly with other real people. It wasn’t over e-mail. It wasn’t over text. It wasn’t over some text-based communication system. It was working one-on-one or team to team. I definitely wanted to prove my worth to the team and we all mutually worked with one another, pushing ourselves very hard to learn a new piece of technology.”

BOOST Opened Up Opportunity

Some graduates shared that the BOOST capstone provided them an opportunity to gain a work-based learning experience in a way that more flexibly worked with their schedule. For instance, one graduate shared that BOOST allowed him to keep working. He stated: “Unfortunately, I wasn’t able to quit my job to participate in a [traditional] internship, [so] this felt kind of like a bite-sized internship.” Other graduates credited the program’s affordability, sharing that it allowed them to participate in a real-world experience while they continued to attend to their caretaking responsibilities. A graduate shared:

“I chose Green River one because it’s cheaper. I was, you know, a single mom kind of in a career transition. And also it was just closer to where I lived than like going to University of Washington. And then finally, I just really liked the idea of doing more of a project-based learning style rather than more of like the textbook-based [learning] that you might get at [a large university].”

Further, one graduate shared that the bachelor’s degree itself is what will open up opportunities for them in the future. They felt that the BAS “broadened their horizons,” opening doors in the future.

They stated: “[A bachelor’s degree is] a minimum; [most companies] wouldn’t even consider you if you were the best software developer in the world if you didn’t have at least a bachelor’s degree.” While their current role and boss doesn’t require them to have a bachelor’s degree, the graduate felt like having the BAS keeps their options open in the future.

Similarly, another graduate credits the capstone in helping them survive a round of layoffs at their current company. He shared that he had gotten a promotion since he started at his job, despite his company going through layoffs at the same time he was being promoted. He attributes his BAS degree in software to keeping him employed.

Resumes, Job Applications, and Landing the Job

All interviewed graduates reported that **they had placed their capstone project on their resumes, and most interviewees felt the experience helped them stand out among other applicants.** One described that the capstone “was by far the best experience on my resume,” and another said that they felt that the “actual real-life project experience helped get me through the initial phase of resume review.” Two graduates shared that the capstone gave them good talking points in their interviews because they had actual software development experience to provide as examples.

Three graduates shared that the open source nature of the project in particular is what stood out to their eventual employers. One shared: “I actually got a job before I graduated, and attribute a lot of that to being able to work on the open source project.” An open source project is complex in nature, working with large codebases, something they felt like their prospective employers had been looking for.

One graduate shared:

“They viewed [my resume] positively because it was unique compared to my other projects because it was working on an existing complex project. [...] They can go and see the actual open source project itself and then they can look and see like, ‘Oh yeah, this is like a big complex project.’”

Another graduate shared that the technical skills they gained in their particular open source project was what opened doors for them. In BOOST, they had worked on an open source project related to chatbots, and that was the main technology that the job they were applying to post-graduation was geared toward. They shared:

“[I know that the capstone helped me] because they told me specifically when they chose me. They’re like, ‘We were looking at a lot of the people who wanted us and we chose you because we’re very interested in the chatbot idea and we saw that you did a couple things like that before.’”

Importantly, another graduate felt like the capstone experience helped them regain employment after losing his job prior to enrolling at GRC. After being laid off in COVID and then going back for this degree, the graduate felt that the skills he learned in the capstone were really valuable to getting a new job. He’s currently back at his former company in a job he got right after graduation. He credits the BAS and experience gained in the BOOST capstone for his new role. He says GRC gave him a lot of technical and project-based experience he could talk about on his resume and in the interview.

Open Source Project Replicated Their Workplace Environment

Once the graduates got through the interview process and landed their jobs, they found that the capstone experience had sufficiently prepared them for what their workplace environments were like.

Several reported that the capstone “more closely mimicked a real job versus student projects.” One graduate found that the workplace didn’t “hold your hand” the way a lot of coursework in his BAS had — that is, aside from the capstone. They shared:

“The [BOOST] capstone kind of felt like it was a sink or swim environment, which was good because you’re getting asked questions, you’re being held to a role of a professional, as opposed to kind of, in school your hands are being held a little bit, which is obviously necessary while you’re learning. If I didn’t do the capstone, I would probably never really feel like I was kind of pushed to the point of knowing I could survive in that kind of environment.”

Others found that the nature of the open source project is what was most closely aligned to their workplace. They described the open source project as large and complex, which is how they characterized their current work too. They described this:

“[My open source project was] a really big project, and I still don’t really understand all of it. But honestly, I think that’s a positive for that experience because my experience in industry so far is that’s how a lot of projects are. They’re very complex and usually you’re just working on a small piece of it and you don’t really understand every single part of it. You just have to focus on the parts you’re working on and the parts that are adjacent to what you’re interacting with. There’s a lot of overlap between [the open source project] and my experience in industry so far.”

Overall, many graduates expressed that the capstone is the closest out of any project that they worked on as a student that felt like how their current work actually feels. Because of the ways in which it mirrors actual work, one graduate recommended all students have a similar capstone experience: “Personally, I think that everybody should have to do an open source contribution during their bachelor’s degree, because I feel like it was the most closely resembling real-world work.”

Preparation for the Workplace

BOOST graduates generally reported feeling prepared for the workplace, in part because of their capstone experience. Some reported that they felt ready to contribute to their projects upon taking the job. In particular, one graduate felt that the process they took during the open source project during their capstone — such as taking a “ticket” or issue, proceeding through a discovery phase, and then making coding changes — was similar to the process they took as a software engineer in their job. They describe this process:

“The process of taking an issue or a ticket or a work item — whatever the team decides to call it — and then going through the discovery phase of ‘what do we need to do?’ and then the work phase where you’re actually making the coding changes and then the PR process — like the whole software development cycle — I feel like it directly translated between that open source project and what I do at work.”

Some felt particularly well-prepared when they compared themselves to their peers at work who started in similar roles at their companies. In comparison to peers in similar roles, they felt they had more confidence as a professional and software developer and that they took on more responsibility in a shorter amount of time than similarly tenured peers. Overall, students felt that they had the technical capability, commitment to do the work, and compatibility with their teams to meaningfully contribute in the workplace.

Promotion Velocity

Several graduates share that they have experienced promotions in their workplace at a higher velocity than their peers, something they attribute to their experience at GRC. One graduate shared that he had had several promotions since beginning work, something his peers had not experienced.

He shared that, of the 20–30 people who started at the same time as he did, he was the only one who really had real-world experience and could engage in technical skills at the intensity his company expected. He was promoted quickly — two times in three years — and only a handful of his initial 20–30 colleagues kept that pace. He attributes his promotions to his capstone experience, describing that he had been so far ahead with real-world applications when he started his role that he was already operating at a higher level than peers, who had plenty of theoretical knowledge but little experience to put it into practice.

Aside from technical skills, other graduates attribute the soft skills they gained during the capstone to their promotion velocity, such as time management skills. In particular, a graduate felt they had gained extensive experience in managing projects during the capstone at GRC, something that proved useful in the workplace and contributed to their quick promotions. The graduate shared:

“I think a lot of the soft skills that you learn through Green River’s program set me up to take off really quickly when I did get the job. We had to learn a lot of things like project management [in the capstone], and for me, when I was in the projects, I was kind of running it for my team, you know, kind of the person making sure that we were meeting all of our deadlines and stuff. It really kind of helped me move quickly through the first level in my first year of work.”

Together, these stories illustrate how GRC’s blend of real-world technical training and soft skills uniquely positioned graduates to advance more rapidly in their careers than their peers.

Conclusion

Recommendations

In the initial developmental evaluation of the BOOST capstone, we provided recommendations relating to scale, sustainability, and stipends. Now with the added data and insights from graduates, we reaffirm these recommendations, along with another related to data collection.

1 Scale

In spring 2025, the first replication of BOOST was conducted at Bellevue College (another community college in the Puget Sound region), in their BS Computer Science program, with an open source Data Engineering project. It will be important to continue to study Bellevue's success with BOOST, as well as test the BOOST model at other community and technical colleges to understand the scale and viability for replication at other institutions. Doing so will provide deeper understanding into the ways in which BOOST works and the possible impact it can have on graduates in the workplace, including helping us to longitudinally understand the impact the BOOST model has on equitable outcomes for underserved populations.

2 Sustainability

Relating to sustainability, and as previously reported, BOOST is dependent on willing champions among faculty, staff, and administration, like program coordinators, program managers, and deans, at colleges to initiate and sustain the work.

While this is still true, we see this model as promising in that it potentially creates a more stable internship experience than traditional employer-sponsored project models because of the mentor relationship and the nature of open source projects. Specifically, open source projects can be continuously sourced and vetted, and mentors can be recruited from the tech workforce and followed from company to company (in contrast to employer-based mentors). Additionally, BOOST graduates themselves can go on to serve as mentors for the program. In fact, several of the interviewed graduates in this study expressed interest in doing so. This combination alleviates some of the turbulence caused by economic conditions or turnover found in traditional employer relationships.

Further, the BOOST approach to sourcing projects and mentors shows potential for sustainability because of the burden it eases off of faculty. In their work, MinT and CodeDay take on the role of workforce intermediaries, the connectors between colleges and mentors who work at potential employers, freeing up time for faculty to focus on teaching and supporting students. This is compared to the traditional internship model, where faculty have to source their own projects and industry partners. This is an oft-unsustainable task, requiring faculty to build and sustain meaningful industry relationships at a level that can fulfill mentorship needs. Finding ways to sustain the workforce intermediary role, in this case fulfilled by MinT and CodeDay, is an important step in alleviating faculty workload, better equipping colleges to sustain this work over the long term.

3 Stipends

We reiterate and underscore our earlier recommendation to focus on fair and reliable stipends for BOOST participants. One of the very few areas of improvement that we heard from graduates was related to confusion, delays, or deferred stipends. One student shared that he thought stipends were a part of the program but was not sure he ever received it. Others were confused if the \$500 stipend was to be split among the student team or allocated for each student individually. This is added to our prior findings, which found that most students were unaware of the stipend until the very end of the experience, begrudgingly assuming during the course of the project that they were engaging in “free labor.” The lack of information about the stipend, confusion about the amount or how it is shared, and the delay or deferment in receiving it could deter students from joining BOOST or negatively impact the experience. Stipends are an important aspect of this work, particularly when it comes to equity for underrepresented students or for students balancing the open source project with other work or family obligations and other course work. As such, we reaffirm the recommendation that greater care and intentionality be brought to this element of the experience.

4 Longitudinal Data Collection

Last, we recommend that the BOOST team bolster its efforts in tracking graduates over time to assess long-term career outcomes, with a focus on advancement, retention, and wage growth. Gathering contact information before graduation, maintaining contact and relationships with students after graduation, disseminating annual surveys to graduates that gather employment, wage, promotion

velocity, and other information related to workforce outcomes and preparedness, and conducting qualitative interviews like those conducted in this study will all help to more fully understand the impact of the BOOST model in the short and long term. Collecting data like this will also help the team compare BOOST alumni outcomes with those of students who did not participate in the experience, strengthening the evidence base for further funding and/or replication.

Limitations

A limitation of this study is the graduate sample size. While the nine graduates interviewed provided a wealth of information and insight into the impact of the BOOST experience, it is not a representative sample. Additional interviews with graduates, including graduates from across graduating classes and from diverse backgrounds, would substantially enrich this data set and lead to new, differing, or corroborating insights.

Concluding Thoughts

While findings are preliminary and limited to nine graduate interviews, early data suggests that the BOOST capstone at Green River College demonstrates that structured, mentored open source projects can provide equitable, workplace-relevant preparation. By combining technical training with professional mentoring, this innovative program equips students with in-demand skills while building the confidence and soft skills needed to thrive in the tech industry. Graduate outcomes, including stronger job readiness and faster promotions, underscore BOOST’s role in accelerating career trajectories. BOOST offers a novel model of work-based learning that, with further resources, funding, and research, could be scalable and more sustainable. These findings position BOOST as both a vital component of GRC’s Software Development program and a promising model for broader adoption at other community and technical colleges seeking to improve equity and workforce readiness in technology fields.

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